

Summary of Insights from WebDocs interviews

Last updated 19 July 2021

Introduction

This document is a summary of preliminary insights deemed salient by the design team within the WebDocs project. The primary objective is to better understand how people use digitized documents held by the KB and National Archives - and repositories of digitized documents in general - or might want to use them in future, as well as for what purposes. Discussions on this topic were situated within a wider dialogue on how people engage with libraries as part of their work in order to better understand how WebDocs fit into everyday activities. Prioritization has been given to items of interest gleaned from team codes applied to examinations of user interviews and co-creation sessions. Due to time restrictions, only five of the interviews have been coded in full, but details from other interviews, team member notes and an online user survey have been included as well. It should be stressed that these insights are **exploratory** and come from a small number of user participants (c. 10 interviews). The purpose here is to highlight prospective areas for further study and development.

Participant characteristics

Interviews were conducted among academic participants coming mainly from humanistic backgrounds, as they were identified as being likely users of the KB and National archives. They represent a wide range of academic experience - one participant having been in the field for fewer than two years and eight stating they have twenty or more years experience. Most are full time researchers in fields such as history, journalism, linguistics and stylometry. Participants also have a diverse level of experience in digital tools, ranging from simple web research, to research conducted through advanced computational research tools, image recognition or contribution to the generation of specialized tools. Participants were primarily Dutch and working at institutions within the Netherlands. One fundamental question asked of participants was the kinds of digitized materials they consult. Their responses have been summarized in the following graph:

Missing resources

The following wordcloud illustrates items mentioned by researchers as part of the resources they analyze but which are not currently held or supported by the KB. In particular it is interesting to notice how several times researchers mentioned three dimensional objects which can be a source of information for researchers and which could be a strategic element to include in the collections of documents which could be consulted through web interfaces. In particular, interviewees mentioned that historical objects often have a cross referencing role because of the connection with the context and period of time studied. Through the engagement with physical objects, researchers often seem to develop a sentimental connection to the element of study because of its physical characteristics. For example, a history researcher has mentioned the possibility that a physical resource allows of learning about printing methodologies through which documents have been produced (therefore also link one historical location to the final users of the historical resource); another humanistic researcher mentioned the curiosity in finding traces of use within the original resource and imagining whether the document has survived previous environmental difficulties.

Resources_summaries

Resources_protected documents

Resources_objects

Resources_Archeological articles

Survey

Following initial discussions among the WebDocs working group, it was decided that a useful first step would be a brief set of probing survey questions which would allow us to gather some basic information from academic users about specific types of interactions they have with digitized documents, particularly those held in the KB. As of 30 June 2021 there were 23 responses. Participants were recruited from professional networks, in particular those relating to Digital Humanities, as well as personal and professional contacts of the WebDocs team. A full set of survey questions and responses is temporarily available [here](#). Some preliminary takeaways from the survey include:

- Academics utilize webdocs for a variety of purposes, from the highly technical (training handwritten text recognition models) to uses beyond the academy (just for fun). Designs should reflect this multiplicity of use.
- Academic users self-identify as being part of a wide variety of disciplines: e.g. art history, media, AI, genetics.
- Access to images and 'texts' appears to be equally valuable.
- A majority of respondents (18/23) state that they use library materials at multiple stages of a research process.
- A small portion of respondents (4/23) use annotation markup tools, and slightly more (7/23) feed webdocs into scripting packages for various purposes.
- All respondents (23/23) indicated that easy access was moderately to extremely important for WebDocs.
- Multiple individual wishes are given in the open response sections, some of which could bear following up:
 - More digitized materials (e.g. dissertations)
 - 'Easier access', including e.g. not having to sign contracts to download datasets
 - Improved OCR (presumably for searchability)

Interviews

The primary source for the insights presented here is a series of interview co-creation sessions conducted by members of the design team with the participants. In total there were ten sessions carried out using a format intended for academic users of WebDocs. During these sessions participants were asked to walk through a series of topics on a Miro board. Topics included habits involving usage of digitized documents held in libraries and archives, but participants were free to deviate from this schema to elaborate on topics they deemed important or relevant to their usage of digitized documents. Participants were encouraged to actively edit the board, though in most cases, for reasons of comfort with the Miro tool, members of the design team annotated the boards while participants spoke. Two initial sessions were done with members of the WebDocs team to test and refine the board content and length. Participants were self-selecting from those who indicated interest when filling in the survey.

Beyond these semi-structured sessions, all members of the group engaged with other users deemed able to make a substantive contribution to discussions of current and future usage of digitized documents. These discussions were largely informal, e.g. email conversations and ad hoc meetings, though some did rely on a set of prompt questions to initiate dialog.

Tools people use with (KB) WebDocs

One facet of experience with digital documents is the tools into which people pull the documents for further use. This small table is a non-exhaustive list of digital tools/textual environments mentioned by users. One possible avenue for further exploration could be to investigate how easy it is to ingest digital documents held by the KB into these tools and whether these processes could be improved in some way. These are presented in no particular order.

Table: User Tools for Exported WebDocs

Name	Type ¹	Notes
Dasha	Text-to-speech	
OCR (generic)	OCR	
ABBYY	OCR	
Transcription software (generic)		
P2Pal	unknown	

¹ These 'types' represent loosely defined clusters intended to illustrate the kinds of work done with web documents. Several tools listed could be categorized as having more than one purpose, and this list is preliminary, not definitive.

Flowy	Database modelling	
iAnnotate	Annotations	
KB Ngram viewer	Analytics	
R/Python packages	Analytics	
Atom	Text editing / Git versioning	
Google translate	Translation	
Screen readers (type?)	Text-to-speech	
Braille interface (generic?)	Translation	
QRead	Reading/Transformation?	
MS Office Suite/Google Docs	Text editing /Note-taking	

Collaboration

Part of the interviews focused on how libraries and active users might collaborate to improve library web documents. Some aspects the participants believe to merit further discussion include:

- Ownership of the documents in digital libraries: what would a co-ownership model of these documents among multiple stakeholders look like?
- Error Correction: Where clear errors are present (above all from the OCR process) users would like the ability to correct these in some simple fashion
- Improve resource query results: when they see that the result and metadata of the search does not match the expected results, users would like to be able to correct the outcomes of resource searches,
- Sharing custom made tools: multiple interviewees build bespoke tools for specific purposes and are interested in others getting further use out of them

Work habits

Physical vs digital resource consultation:

Interviewed users are avid in their resource consultation, one element of pride that they take is visible through mentions of the amount of their digital and physical resources and in the satisfaction that they are able to decide and maneuver around the large amounts of documents throughout different research activities while simultaneously valuing their freedom in partaking of such activities.

User responses through follow-up interviews show that although the digitization of resources has still to be improved on the side of accessibility of certain resources, e.g. regarding the bureaucracy, copyright and trustworthiness of OCR technologies, researchers already follow a mostly digital workflow. Even the ones that have had a traditional, pre-digitization education have transitioned towards digital research. One participant went so far as to state 'Whenever I get something on paper, I digitize it' (Interview 3).

Researchers who are still using a mostly physical work method value time efficiency in direct contact with the physical document, along with the possibility to jump to sections of the document as needed without having to do multiple searches to get to the chapter/section that they already know. Furthermore, digital reading tools are perceived as a limitation of note-taking; elements and sections can be exported for the creation of an individual database, but in-text note-taking, advanced highlighting and 'doodling' is not easily savable and are therefore perceived as less reliable for subsequent consultation and review.

Individual work but with valuable collaboration

Although the main research activities of most participants are conducted alone, collaboration with other researchers has been mentioned by the majority of participants as an activity that contributes significantly to the development, discovery and improvement of research outcomes. Collaboration seems to have a key role in the discovery of new resources to consult and in the elaboration of text for clarifications and fact checking, which occurs once individual researchers draft an initial version of a document.

The reason why researchers view and conduct research mostly individually seems to be related to a matter of habit, as is a tendency to share and ask for reciprocal consultation only in cases where another researcher has a deeper understanding of a given topic. The creative process of new idea generation seems to take place during individual work until the moment of saturation from the individual work and necessity of reciprocal stimulation through discussion. At the same time, collaboration seems to be perceived as a possibility for spreading information, and more rarely, as a possibility for creation of new material.

'Either you work as teams so that you can pool resources and do this for a group and do this for a larger community, or you do it individually and the problem with humanities is that most people still work individually. They're not used to working in groups' (Interview 3)

Methodologies adopted for research goal achievement in current practice

Interviews also highlighted several methods used by researchers for resource discovery, resource scoping, resource analysis, and composition of results.

Resource discovery

Research practices involving digitized documents are not always executed within a strictly defined framework. Researchers can pass from one area to another driven by *serendipitous discovery* of resources or subjects (mentioned twice). This unplanned stumbling upon a new

resource takes place in the less frequented sections of a library, by looking at references mentioned by other researchers in the field, curious discovery and research expansion. The serendipitous discovery seems to be more easily achievable in a physical setting due to the lower amount of barriers through which a user must pass. The physical placement of resources in library environments forces the researcher to wander and investigate in order to arrive at the location of a resource instead of presenting it as a result of a query as in digital interfaces.

A slightly less emotionally attractive but more frequent possibility is that of discovery of resources *through word of mouth* (mentioned three times). This can happen both through discussion with fellow researchers at the library coffee bar or other physical settings, or through recommendations of resources from collaborators and fellow researchers. This methodology of resource discovery is also perceived as highly valuable because of its reliance on other expert knowledge and the type of resources being specifically directed towards a unique, individual goal.

Participants mentioned that also *through the activity of resource analysis* resource discovery can occur cyclically and take place in the moment a resource is mentioned in bibliography or footnotes. In the case of digitized documents, where links between resources are done correctly, digital tools present an advantage over their physical counterpart. However, as mentioned in multiple interviews, not many resources have been linked correctly and consistently.

In-text resource discovery also happens when a researcher goes from one resource to another *by discovering connections* between resources within a specific topic. In this last method, the researcher initiates a new query intrigued by a certain topic or mention.

Resource scoping

One crucial phase of research consists in selecting what resources to use through the process of analysis. This is oftentimes a sensitive step, since resources can be either too numerous to assess in order to scope down with full awareness or else difficult to locate in the first place. Interview participants highlighted both scenarios but mentioned that in both cases their solution to an appropriate scoping of the resource pool is to rely on their experience and feeling developed through the years. For example, one participant (Interview 4), working in linguistic and historical analysis of correspondence, mentioned that based on experience they would separate a topic into a low number of levels of categories and populate them with a determined amount of resources per category. The number of categories varies depending on the extremeness of polarization he wants to analyze, while the number of resource samples per category is an amount he has determined as giving enough validation to each category.

One interesting remark appeared concerning a perceived trend of reversing difficulty in terms of scoping resource pools: for now resource pools have to be sifted due to the time consumption related to going through resources, but in the future, thanks to the support of technologies this objective may be streamlined if it becomes possible to facilitate the selection of valuable resources within the vast amount of resources available.

Resource analysis

Resource analysis is the research phase which takes the majority of the time because of its demands for attention to detail. Researchers have several ways to go through resources which reflect their personal points of focus and methods of combination of information. Generally speaking, however, it is possible to abstract at least four clusters of activities: selection of relevant information, elaboration of information, information extraction, database creation.

Through their different areas of application, users mostly still adopt the traditional method of scrolling through a document either reading fast or only paying attention to certain words or concepts by performing selective searches of topic-specific terms. Some users mentioned a habit of going through the text several times but putting attention each time to a different aspect of the text. The traditional document skimming is done concurrently with an activity of making highlights of the relevant elements within the document. Multiple researchers use digital tools to make highlights, with two focus points which generally indicate a different interest: either on single words for more linguistic analysis relative to a semantic meaning or orthographic use of a word or on entire phrases for more focus on the content and context. The use of different colouring is appreciated in the case of highlighting because it gives the opportunity to separate topics and already start a process of clustering. Since no participant mentioned the serendipitous discovery of relevant concepts, it seems that researched topics are mostly already known at the beginning of the resource analysis.

Some participants mentioned a distrust towards use of automated text analysis, mostly because of past poor experiences and a possible gap in the understanding of how the automated text analysis functions or what additional possibilities it could open if used properly.

In the event that research focuses more on content to be used for writing papers, users tend to jump more through the paragraphs and chapters, already understanding from the starting pages whether or not they could find support for their research in the different sections of the resource.

While it is usually possible to skip through a document through its table of contents, it could be interesting to allow also the selection and deselection of sections of the document to be displayed in order to shorten/lengthen the document but still retain a general overview. Some users have stated that skipping through a physical document could be quicker than using a digital document because of technical problems of loading of images and pages when going through a digital document.

At the end of the activity of note-taking and highlighting, relevant quotes are exported for further reading and processing in personalized digital databases. These databases are mostly stored on users' local computers and have been created by the users themselves for very personalized aims: some just export quotations clustered into topics; others fill a scheme where they summarize metadata information and selection criteria relative to the document. Others who focus more on the physical analysis of manuscripts and resources

annotate information regarding the physical state of the pages, printing methodology used for the resource production, notes left on the side of the pages by original owners, etc. These types of details are relevant for the purpose of gathering information about the resource context. Databases generally have a tabular and list appearance. However, it could be interesting to note that one participant also expressed his greater comfort in organizing information in a visual manner in order to avoid getting lost into the big amount of information.

Interviewed researchers make extensive use of OCR tools through the resource analysis step. This technology is highly relevant to the humanistic researchers studying scanned resources, which are then transcribed and analyzed. Difficulties and errors contained in the OCR tools are tied to time efficiency problems in the resource analysis step, which often results in an additional step of correction of the OCR results.

Composition of results

The final stage of the research consists generally in the composition of relevant insights. Depending on the activity done by the researcher this results either in less structured documents such as lecture slides and documents, or fully referenced works such as papers for publications or books. This stage has been less mentioned in detail by interviewed participants as it consists of an ongoing process that is actively undertaken during the resource analysis step and is finalized by further development of material following the researcher's mental mindmap. Therefore, it seems that what the researcher's value at this stage is the complete freedom to mix and match patches of resources gathered, link concepts analyzed and, through the process, discover new links to further develop.

Several interviewed users mentioned the creation of lecture material and how they noticed students and junior researchers could benefit more from the creation of a digital environment which could help them in the final stage of result composition. Existing tools appear to assist researchers more in the stages of resource finding and analysis, while the result composition appears to be in an environment slightly separate and taking place usually on researcher's own computers, less cloud based and created through tools developed by researcher's themselves instead of being supported by a more structured framework. The reason for choosing to rely on a separate framework reflects both the researcher's high value for their own organizational freedom and the fact that notes and highlights get easily lost between sessions when using digital tools as well as copyright problems connected to the ownership of data relative to resources.

Result composition consists also of the integration both of digital resources into the document being created and in the merging of insights across several resources. This final step is highly iterative and benefits the most from the collaborative nature of research: researchers get back in contact with each other in order to both discuss resource interpretations and give each other peer reviews or approval.

Wishes

The figure below represents a short list of tools and actions which interviewees expressed a desire to have. Contents of the list represent a selection by the interview assessors.

Some brief explanatory notes on the 'wishes' given in the figure:

- Granular citation: This refers to an ability to refer to specific parts of a WebDoc, for instance a set of lines or a page.
- Thesaurus of synonyms: A type of 'concept' or 'semantic' search wherein a search would yield both results to the search query and to terms 'similar' to the query
- Personalized workspace: A digital area where people could import materials and manipulate them as desired. Broadly similar to a VRE (virtual research environment).
- Segment downloads: Several users have mentioned that they would like to be able to download citations from resources. Their wish is also related to content embedded into images which they would like to export and download directly from the digital viewer, without the need to download the entire resource. One user mentioned how the functionality of retrieving segments of a quotation from resources is especially user friendly within the iOS application iAnnotate where, after clustering insights by means of highlights of different colours users can download them directly, already clustered into a pdf document or send the document to collaborators through email.
- Transfer of reading experience into digital tools: As mentioned above, resources carry with them more information than text and images. Some characteristics of the physical document are harder to view in the digitized versions of resources. In a physical document images and layouts are created in different sizes, fitting the initial will of the publisher and the format of the resource revealing meanings of significance and context of use. In the digitized version of a document, every section and the entire book is resized to fit the format of the screen through which the document is consulted, which makes it hard to understand what was the initial size of the document. This is especially relevant to history archive researchers who analyze and study printing techniques and characteristics of older documents. One participant expressed that zoom functions are fundamental for digital interfaces and that everything has to load quickly, mimicking the speed and precision of having a simple magnifying glass in a reading room.

Researchers mainly focusing on manuscripts mentioned that visual features add context and depth to the text, and it is considered a pity that documents' visual features could get lost if they are not scanned properly or if they are only transcribed, because certain research activities are then no longer possible.

The experience of a physical document also has sentimental value, as it brings with itself the attached history of how long it has persisted and the vicissitudes it has endured to come down to the hand of the researcher. A few participants mentioned how they appreciate a sense of ownership of a physical consultation or book. Lastly, one characteristic of the experience of a library consultation is that of gathering together people with the same background or interest who might, in addition to the social bond, act as a natural filter to the amount of resources that could be consulted ideally on a determinate topic.

- Flexibility of search: One important element to consider when we take into account humanistic and historical research is that some old manuscripts and documents have been transcribed with initial digital techniques. In some early writings there was no set orthography, so there were many different ways to spell a word or different words to express the same concept. For these reasons several times it has been mentioned by interviewees that it is highly necessary to be able to both search within a text, and

also set flexibility parameters within the search in order to indicate alternative synonyms and different spellings, both within a text as well as for resource query.

- Search cross-referencing: The ability to search multiple texts/corpora at the same time as desired, especially those housed in multiple institutions/libraries.
- Researcher's collaboration on content: Most of the available tools are built and refined by computer scientists, addressing needs of researchers based on user studies. However, being built by a different type of user at the end of the process, and due of limitations of time and funding, they often end up reflecting some characteristics that are not fully aligned with the needs of researchers, resulting often in an outdated tool which is still not fully satisfying. For this reason some more technologically educated interviewees expressed their wish for involvement into the creation and setting of the content of tools, as well as the possibility for access to their code in a later stage, in order to be able to adapt the tools to new or personal needs.
- Annotation databases: Some means of extracting annotated items into a structured form

Pain points

Items in the list below are gleaned from discussions during the interviews in which the participant expressed a frustration with an existing part of the process. (N.b. the colours reflect a set of categories created by the assessors and can be ignored here)

Access to documents and unreliable OCR are two significant concerns mentioned by multiple participants. Access is a broad term and can refer to a range of issues from searching/discovery, digital availability, copyright hindrances and other, related issues. Lack of OCR reliability refers primarily to full-texts, where available, not meeting user expectations in terms of similarity to the scanned physical document.

Future vision of the library

This small wordcloud is a representation based on parts of discussions regarding the future roles of the library with respect to WebDocs. Multiple participants indicate that they foresee the library becoming increasingly digital and as a place where digital collections are stored and used in some way. They also seem to view it as a trusted network hub to which people can connect their own tools and systems. While views of the future library seem to be quite positive overall with improvements in access and connectivity, there are some small but notable concerns of possible downsides, such as a loss of serendipitous discovery through digital materials as less common end up in 'dark archives' hidden in mass lists of search results or not easily findable at all.

Future thinking - trusted information

Future thinking - Availability for the blind

Future thinking - Collaboration between institutions

Future thinking - cross referencing resources

Future thinking - Increased digitization

Future thinking- creating own tools

Future thinking - facilitate advanced searches

Future Thinking - Less serendipity in research

Conceptualization of possible interface setups and features

During the interviews participants were asked to co-create a possible interface which could facilitate the types of research activities performed involving WebDocs. Particular emphasis was given to resource analysis. The figure below is a snapshot of multiple co-created interfaces collected during the interviews through the Miro board, and the following word cloud presents aspects and features participants mentioned as being valuable to these interfaces.

- Possibility of writing annotations as comments in text margins.
- The possibility of saving such highlights and annotations in a personal space
- Built-in dictionaries for various purposes (e.g. historical languages)
- View of specific metadata within the search results
- Ability to highlight in different colours
- Export and download (through email) of specific parts of text or images

Interface Conceptualization

By combining relevant insights from the interviews with the co-creation interface efforts done by participants through the interviews it has been possible to create an initial conceptualization of a WebDoc overall interface, it can be visualized at [this](#) Figma link. This concept can be used as an explanatory tool to analyze the different experiences and interactions observed. And should be therefore considered as a proposal for further investigation on level of relevance of features, and eventual detailing.

Site map

The web interface can be composed of six interfaces, all accessible from a tab bar at the top of the site. The website pages should keep data saved also when the user switches from one tab to the other if a logged in session is taking place. As described in the figure below, there are different levels of access to information: 'public pages', which are not personalized, are accessible directly to all website visitors, 'Member only' pages are accessed only with a profile and allow to be personalized and save data on a cloud, 'shared between users', which, although being personalized results, can be accessed also through a link. Finally, certain content, marked in yellow, is relative to integration of content coming from different sites within a web page. Within the different tabs (described in the second row of the sitemap), certain content can be identified as well as being of public, personalized or external domain.

Main page

The main page is relative to a welcoming page to users, where users can access through a login section, learn about current and future events (digital or happening at the KB buildings), see links to other libraries, and perhaps learn about the library network. This page might take the role of replacing the current social and informative functionalities nowadays carried out from the library as a physical space.

Resource browser

This tab is used for resource finding, mainly at the start of the research in order to find and make the first screening of the main resource corpus. The main functionalities of this tab are: search feature, resource display, resource actions.

The screenshot displays the 'RESOURCE BROWSER' interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: 'WebDocs', 'Search Resources', 'Resource Scoping', 'Resource Analysis', 'Composition', and a user profile 'Floyd Miles'. The main search area includes a search bar with 'Enter Search Term', an '+ Add Term' button, and a 'Search' button. A checkbox for 'Include inflected terms' is checked, with a note: 'Finds all inflected forms of a word. For example, searching for "run" will automatically include paragraphs with "running", "runs" and "ran". Choose inflection dictionary'. Below the search bar, there are filters for 'Order result by' (Least read, Most recent) and 'Current filters (3): Only Dutch results, Published, mm/dd/yyyy - mm/dd/yyyy, containing images'. The results are displayed in a table with columns: Document, Document Code, Digitization date, Publication date, Authors, Typology, and Pages. Three results are shown, all with the same title 'Resource Title' and code '86f78e30-1c'. Each result includes a 'Document images preview', a 'Scan preview', and a 'Transcription preview'. The transcription text for all three is: 'The long barrow was built on land previously inhabited in the Mesolithic period. It consisted of a sub-rectangular earthen tumulus, estimated to have been 15 metres (50 feet) in length, with a chamber built from sarsen megaliths on its eastern end. Both inhumed and cremated human remains were placed within this chamber during the Neolithic period, representing at least nine or ten individuals.' The typology for the first result is 'Manuscript, Ink on chinese Paper' (34 pages), for the second is 'Early printed book, Book printing method' (980 pages), and for the third is 'Letters, Ink on Paper' (4 pages). A 'TOOLS' sidebar on the right contains various functions: Resource discovery (Advanced Search, Group Discussion), Metadata settings (Timer, Add tool), Image analysis (Snippet, Measure), Text analysis (Highlight, Speak out loud, Comment, Draw, N Viewer, Input text).

Search feature: As seen earlier, the main resource browser tool, the search feature, should allow users for complete flexibility, allowing them to query multiple nouns or phrases at a time (by increasing the number of words with the '+add term' button) and therefore include different semantic expressions and orthographies. By tagging the 'include inflected terms' flag users could add additional variability to the search including also declinations of the searched term. For example, if a user would search the term 'run', including inflected terms would mean including terms such as 'running', 'ran', 'runs'. The dictionary used for inflection should be customizable and could be also related to a specific location and period of time. The order of display of results could as well be customized to show resources ordered, in an ascending or descending order, based on their novelty and popularity, allowing in this way to satisfy also researchers in search for the most rare and unknown resources easily. Filtering of resources should also be possible, in order to help browsing through the immense amounts of results. Filters could restrict resources by date of publication, library availability, type of library, resource category, authors, content characteristics, just to mention a few possible examples.

Resource display:

In the list of resources the user can choose to display elements of interest additionally to the main descriptive metadata. An example taken from interview outcomes is to have already a preview of the images contained within the document, of the digitized scan of the document and of the transcription. This possibility of preview would allow users to identify which document to select without the need to open the resource link and would therefore speed-up the process.

Resource actions:

In addition to the basic feature of opening resources to visualize the content, at this process stage users could also benefit from few additional actions:

- Simple resource save: being the equivalent to picking up a document from a bookshelf, this action would simply save the resource in the list of picked resources with whom the user would like to interact further later on.
- Resource categorization: Through a follow-up pop up, this button allows users to assign a specific resource to a specific project and a cluster of resources within the list of selected resources for the project.
- Add comment: The user could want to add a comment to the resource at the moment of saving the resource in the resource list.

- Sent: In order to get feedback or start a conversation, users could want to send a specific resource to a colleague/fellow researcher through email.
- Signal mistake: users could find a result of the query unrelated to a query. In order to improve future query results they could want to signal this to the research community.
- Download: in case of a personal preference for consultation, users could want to download a resource locally.

Selected resources tab

During interviews researchers expressed the need for more structure within their process of selection and filtering of resources, for this purpose the tab 'Selected resources' was ideated. Here users can visualize the saved items and continue the clustering process, which can happen both manually, or be assisted by automated systems (e.i. Cluster resources containing a certain term co-occurrence. In this tab, which is only personal, users can also upload personal resources.

WebDocs Search Resources Resource Scoping Resource Analysis Composition Floyd Miles

SELECTED RESOURCES

Project: The role of religion in commercial affairs
Total number of resources : 90 Documents

Upload document Create new cluster Cluster by Select preferences

Cluster: Analyze first 45 items

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: This is relevant to that

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: Something someone wrote here to know something more about that

Resource Title
K. Nobody..
No comment

Resource Title

Cluster: Bad images 12 items

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: This is relevant to that

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: Something someone wrote here to know something more about that

Resource Title
K. Nobody..
No comment

Resource Title

Cluster: Related to Contiousness topic 26 items

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: This is relevant to that

Resource Title
A. Someone, M. Notarealname, K. Nobody..
Comment: Something someone wrote here to know something more about that

Resource Title
K. Nobody..
No comment

Resource Title

Saved but unclustered resources: 90 Documents

Resource Title 86f78e30-1c 9/23/16 9/23/16 A. Bhattacharya, M. Hui, K. Ellen Foley... Manuscript, Ink on chinese Paper 34

Document images preview Scan preview Transcription preview

The long barrow was built on land previously inhabited in the Mesolithic period. It consisted of a sub-rectangular earthen tumulus, estimated to have been 15 metres (50 feet) in length, with a chamber built from sarsen megaliths on its eastern end. Both inhumed and cremated human remains were placed within this chamber during the Neolithic period, representing at least nine or ten individuals.

TOOLS

Resource discovery
Advanced Search Group Discussion
Metadata settings
Timer Add tool

Image analysis
Snippet Measure
Add tool

Text analysis
Highlight Speak out loud
Comment Draw
N Viewer Input text

Resource analysis tab

When opening a resource, users enter a new tab which allows them to interact with a specific resource. Important features of this tab are: comparison layer, navigation characteristics, interactions with content.

WebDocs Search Resources Resource Scoping Resource Analysis Composition Floyd Miles

Resource Title Compare Transcription

Supplement III

The long barrow was built on land previously inhabited in the Mesolithic period. It consisted of a sub-rectangular earthen tumulus, estimated to have been 15 metres (50 feet) in length.

- The long barrow was built on land previously inhabited in the Mesolithic period.
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Supplement III

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Links within text

Dictionary Zoom in Zoom out Notepad Pan Add comparison window Shrink window to the side Open Language keyboard

TOOLS

Resource discovery

Advanced Search Group Discussion

Metadata settings

Timer Add tool

Image analysis

Snippet Measure

Add tool

Text analysis

Highlight Speak out loud

Comment Draw

N Viewer Input text

Comparison layer: Through the buttons 'add comparison window' and 'shrink comparison window' the user should be able to interact either only with the scanned document or simultaneously also with a different document version to be picked of their choice (e.g. a translation of the text, a transcription, a different edition of the same resource, etc.). On this note, it could be a source of further ideation that one interviewed researcher also mentioned the interest of comparing one resource with a different resource on top, in a sort of transparency layer mode.

Navigation characteristics: Users mentioned several times the importance of the possibility of zooming within the document scans, it is important that the documents are loading with high resolution and with ease also at high zoom percentages. If a comparison window has been opened, the zooming, panning and navigation through the document should be coordinated with the navigation in the comparison window. Researchers also mentioned an opportunity which is not yet developed enough by digital libraries and tools: taking advantage of the use of links. This can be related both to footnotes and cross referencing between resources but also to the linking to external resources. For example, if the resource text is mentioning a 'chamber made of sarsen megalith' a footnote box at the corner of the image could display more information or images of the mentioned historical structure.

Interaction with content: At the moment of scanning through a document researchers tend to highlight, draw and comment on the analyzed elements, or take snippets of scanned pages. These interactions should be saved in the personal experience of the user with the

visualized document also for further consultation sessions. Furthermore, it is necessary that interactions are also shareable with other researchers (through sending a snippet or quotation directly through email or giving access to the document through a sharable link). One last interaction to note, enabled through the 'input text' button is the possibility to correct OCR or translation mistakes in case of notice, and share those corrections with the library users community.

Composition tab

Similarly to the Resource Analysis Tab, the Composition Tab is a proposal for giving more support in the overall interactions with resources, as it has been mentioned as a relevant need by multiple participants. In this tab the user would be able to compose a text document or a database table and at the same time visualize a list of snippets, citations and resources analysed in the previous phases. Interaction should be facilitated by allowing to filter the displayed elements by clusters or notes, colour of highlight or cluster of resources.

Personal library tab

Finally, the personal library tab allows users to review their different projects, conversations and personalized tools. In this section, more advanced researchers could also explore tools shared by other researchers in order to learn more and expand their capabilities. This characteristic would allow researchers to obtain a GitHub-like environment, mentioned a few times by more tech savvy participants.

Projects

Lexicon and Bibliography: Meaning and Concept	Private	78 Documents	21 Sep, 2020
Fusce id velit ut tortor	Private	34 Documents	1 Feb, 2020
Dui vivamus arcu felis bibendum	Private	302 Documents	17 Oct, 2020
Ultrices mi tempus imperdiet nulla	Private	21 Documents	22 Oct, 2020
Aliquet risus feugiat in ante	Shared with 1	13 Documents	24 May, 2020

Conversations 24

Darlene Robertson	In fermentum posuere urna nec	Consequat volutpate velit esse cillum dolore eu feugiat nulla pariatur. Duis aute irure dolor in	8 Sep, 2020
Bessie Cooper	Diam in arcu cursus euismod	Ullamco laboris nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in reprehenderit in	1 Feb, 2020
Cameron Williamson	Mi quis hendrerit dolor magna	Amet minim mollit non deserunt ullamco est sit aliqua dolor do amet sint. Velit officia consequat	22 Oct, 2020
Jerome Bell	Aliquet risus feugiat in ante	Consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua.	22 Oct, 2020
Eleanor Pena	Ultrices mi tempus imperdiet nulla	Nemo enim ipsam voluptatem quia voluptas sit aspernatur aut odit aut fugit, sed quia consequuntur	17 Oct, 2020

Tool discovery

New

Most popular

For this

For that

My tools

Toolbar

A few actions cross over between phases of research and could therefore be useful across different tabs. Because of this, tools can be displayed on a 'tool column' on the side of the main content of each tab, which offers also the possibility to add custom made tools and functionalities. Remarks on some of the tools currently proposed:

- **Advanced search feature:** As mentioned previously, users tend to read texts multiple times with a new focus for each read. Because of this, they may additionally benefit from the ability to create complex combined or independent queries simultaneously, ideally with a level of flexibility through the search in order to accommodate the freedom of semantic research or queries with a level of variation of the individual word's orthography. This search feature could also output citations highlighted in different colours, to be visualized both in an external quotation summary and in-text, in order to be able to visualize the correlations between different concepts and queried terms. This tool is mainly going to be used in the Resource Analysis Tab, but possible uses can be imagined across multiple resources in the Resource Browser and Resource Scoping tabs.
- **Group discussion:** Collaboration with other researchers is not currently very frequent in the research sector, although the possibility of collaboration sporadically offers great advantages for researchers. For this reason a 'Group discussion' call button could be an interesting feature to implement for facilitating peer confrontation at any moment and on demand.
- **Timer:** One pain point for researchers is the lack of time to assess a great amount of resources, or on the other extreme, the long procedure of requesting the availability

of a resource. In both cases it could be an advantage to allow users to assign a duration for a task.

- **N Viewer:** Tech savvy researchers have mentioned additionally the use of specific tools for the analysis of texts. One example is the use of the NGram Viewer, which also analyzes information such as the frequency of words or the frequency of consecutive words.

Future work

Several potential directions for further work concerning web documents arise on the basis of the insights presented here. Here are three broad themes, each of which encompasses multiple topics mentioned above.

- Focus: Access

WebDocs users seem to prefer to import materials into other tools during one or more phases of their work. Most seem content with the current formats provided by the KB and ask for more holdings to be digitized and that barriers to access be removed where possible.

Some possible routes to explore include investigating novel ways for people to interrogate the vast holdings of the KB. Are there ways we might open up full-text searches and appropriate filters to allow for more targeted research? Is there a way to facilitate serendipitous encounters?

- Focus: Quality

Several people who focus on text remarked on the desire for 'improved OCR'. This may be translated as a wish for the machine-readable text to be more similar to how a human perceives words on the page. This includes both accuracy of the written content and appropriate structures for a variety of purposes. Both are large tasks, but they may be broken up into a series of smaller pilot projects to test functions and feasibility. One such task might be to determine how difficult it is to render a single, unstructured document of plain text into DAISY format, but there are several others.

- Focus: Connections

One way to view the future of digitized collections within libraries is as trusted network hubs. This model, which has long served libraries in physical manifestations, has the capacity to grow in future by building further digital networks to increase both quantity and richness. Here we might consider how libraries could re-incorporate enrichments produced by users, both in terms of content (e.g. metadata, OCR corrections) and means of exploiting this content (e.g. links to bespoke analysis tools). It may also become a strong mandate for libraries to facilitate digital interactions of users on users' own terms, which could mean further opening up library infrastructures to make them 'hackable' or otherwise customizable to suit the plethora of actions academic users conduct both now and in future.

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